

IMPACT PROPERTIES OF GLASS/EPOXY PLATES REINFORCED WITH METAL FIBRES

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SUMMARY

This paper presents an overview low velocity impact tests performed in assessing the feasibility of selectively reinforcing glass/epoxy composites with metal fibres. It is shown that the addition of very low volume fractions of metal fibres can significantly reduce the absorbed energy and damage area of the laminate.

Keywords: metal fibres, fibre reinforced plastics, low velocity impact

INTRODUCTION

Composite structures are often subjected to low velocity impacts which can result in extensive damage. Even at relatively low impact energies many damage modes are possible, such as matrix crushing, cracking, delamination and fibre breakage. The point at which damage begins to occur within the composite laminate significantly reduces residual mechanical properties, and hence the importance of keeping the level of damage to a minimum by increasing damage resistance.

Several methods have been employed to improve the impact behaviour of fibre reinforced polymer composites, such as matrix toughening, fibre hybridising and 3-D composites. This investigation takes the hybridising approach to improvement in impact properties through the incorporation of metal wires into the laminate, where the ductility of the metal wires is the most obvious property to be exploited. The ability of the metal wires to plastically deform could be beneficial in the event of impact, as plastic deformation is an extra energy absorption mechanism, thus reducing the energy that would otherwise cause delaminations and fibre breakage.

The idea of embedding a more ductile fibre, such as aramid or polyethylene, has been investigated in the literature with varying degrees of success. Shape memory alloy (SMA) wires hybridised with carbon fibres have also been investigated [1]. It was shown that only 2.8% volume fraction of embedded SMA wires resulted in a decrease in damage area of up to 25% compared to plain laminates. However, these wires were relatively large at 0.3mm diameter and thus constituted a considerable proportion of the thickness of the overall laminate (1.63mm), making it difficult to differentiate between the effect of the metal inclusion and thickness effects. The impact performance of stainless steel metal wires in epoxy has been investigated previously by Ross *et al.*[2] and compared to that of glass/epoxy. A difference in failure mechanism was found to exist between the two types of laminate but a direct comparison of impact behaviour in terms of absorbed energy and damage area was not made.

Previous literature has provided a good indication that improvements in impact behaviour are possible with fibre hybridising. Therefore, it was the aim of this study to investigate the effect of hybridising glass fibres with metal wires on the overall laminate behaviour under low-velocity impact.

EXPERIMENTAL DETAILS

E-glass fibre rovings of 800 tex and AISI304 stainless steel fine wires of 100µm diameter were used as the reinforcement. In addition, Epikote 4908 resin and hardener were used for the epoxy matrix.

Production method

Crossply laminates were filament wound over a stainless steel mould using an automated filament winding machine. Initially, three metal wires were wound together in the 0° direction at a spacing of once every 2.5mm for 160mm, and then once every 1.25mm for 160mm. The mould was then rotated 90 ° and the procedure repeated. Figure 1(a) shows details of the metal wire arrangement, where it is clear that nine 160x160mm sections were produced containing various amounts of wires. In one section, labelled "7" in the figure, there were no wires. It is also clear from the production process and the figure that laminates 1 and 9, 2 and 6, and 4 and 8 contained the same amount of wires and will be verified in the Results section.

Glass rovings were filament wound above the wires, as shown in Figure 1(b). Four layers were wound in total with a lay-up of [0/90]₂. The mould and contents were then bagged in preparation for the vacuum infusion process, Figure 1(c). Finally, the epoxy resin and hardener were mixed according to the manufacturer's specifications and vacuum-infused at 20mbars until the contents were fully impregnated. The vacuum was then raised to 500mbars to reduce the size of any voids present and left to cure in this condition for at least 24 hours. A 4 hour post-cure at 80 °C completed the production process. An electric mini-saw was used to cut the edges of the cured laminate to release two identical plates from the mould, as shown in Figure 1(d). Each of the plates were cut using a diamond saw into nine 120x120mm sections.

To compare the laminates, density measurements were performed according to ASTM D792. Volume fraction measurements were also performed according to the burn-off test outlined in ASTM D2584. The metal wires were extracted by hand from the dry glass fibres and weighed separately.

Impact test method

The drop-weight impact tower employed in this study consisted of a double column impactor guide mechanism that releases an impactor at the desired height. A hemispherical tup of 16mm diameter was used and the entire impactor had a 931.4g mass. The contact force between the impactor and the specimen was measured by a load cell placed in the impactor tup. A circular test geometry of 80mm diameter with eight bolts clamped at 30Nm torque was used as the holding jig for the impact specimens.

Figure 1 Details of the production procedure

The laminate plates were impacted from one of up to four heights, 95cm, 115cm, 175cm and 215cm, corresponding to 7J, 10J, 13J and 17J respectively, in order to impart varying degrees of damage. The laminates were impacted either with the metal wires facing the impactor (top side) or on the opposite side (bottom side). Force-time and force-deflection were directly obtained during the impact event. Absorbed energy was obtained from the integration of the force-deflection plot.

Laminate analyses

Samples were taken from each of the sections for volume fraction analysis using the resin burn-off method described in ASTM D2584. After the burn-off procedure the glass and metal wires were weighed together. The metal wires were then hand-picked from the dry glass fibres and were weighed separately. The individual weights were checked against the original combined weight to ensure that no glass was inadvertently removed. The weight and hence volume fraction was then calculated according to the standard.

After impact, the damage area was obtained from ultrasonic c-scanning. In some cases, the laminates were cut across the damage area and examined using optical microscopy.

RESULTS

Laminate analyses

After release from the mould the laminates were cut and inspected. As a consequence of the vacuum infusion method, the mould side of the laminate was smooth whereas the opposite side was very rough due to the peel ply and bagging materials. The metal wires were wound first on the mould and hence were on the "smooth side" of the laminate. It will be shown in the results that the surface of the laminate had an influence on its impact performance.

Cross-sections of the various laminates were examined under the microscope and are shown in Figure 2. During winding, the metal wires could not be kept equidistant from each other as the smooth surface of the mould allowed some unavoidable movement after placement. This resulted in the seemingly random distribution of the metal wires seen in the figures.

Figure 2(a) and (b) show examples of laminate cross-sections with the metal wires placed unidirectionally. Under greater magnification, the former figure shows two distinct layers, one of the metal wire/epoxy and the other of the glass fibre/epoxy (henceforth called the wire layer and glass layer, respectively). This occurred when the wires were placed perpendicularly to the next layer of glass fibres. The latter figure shows no separate layers, where the wires were laid in parallel with the glass fibres. During the winding process the glass fibres settled around the metal wires, effectively embedding them in the same layer.

Figure 2(c) and (d) show examples of laminate cross-sections with a 0/90 arrangement of the metal wires. Again under greater magnification two distinct layers can be seen of the wires and the glass fibres. Both laminates display a thicker wire layer with little visual difference between them.

The thickness of each laminate plate was measured and the metal wire weight and volume fraction calculated. The results are shown in Table 1 with laminates 1 and 9, 2 and 6, and 4 and 8 grouped together in order to highlight their similar metal content and wire arrangement. Laminates 1 and 4 were slightly thinner than laminates 9 and 8 due to the settling effect described previously. However, it will be shown that the differences in impact performance were not significantly affected by the different wire arrangement. Laminate 3 was thicker than any of the crossply laminates, which arose due to the closer average spacing of the wires. Waviness of the wires in one layer due to those underneath, and vice versa, was kept to a minimum, hence resulting in a thicker laminate. The density of laminate 3 was also the greatest, and the addition of 1.9% volume fraction resulted in an increase of 3% over that of the plain laminate 7. The new nomenclature assigned to the laminates is listed in the Table.

Impact tests - metal wires on top face

Figure 3(a) shows the absorbed energy versus impact energy graph for the laminates impacted with the metal wires on the top (smooth) face. The plain laminates were also tested with the smooth face towards the impactor. With increasing impact energy, the

Figure 2 Microscope images at 2.5x (left) and 10x (right) magnification of laminate cross-sections.

Table 1 Plate details: UD is unidirectional, CP is crossply and V_f is volume fraction

Plate number	Wire UD/CP	Plate thickness (mm)	Glass V_f (%)	Metal V_f (%)	Density (g/cm^3)	New name
4	UD	2.04	65.5	0.52	2.112	UD_low
8		2.10	65.2	0.49	2.117	
1	UD	2.05	64.4	1.01	2.109	UD_high
9		2.10	64.1	1.00	2.124	
2	CP	2.12	61.2	1.44	2.114	CP_med
6		2.13	61.2	1.43	2.109	
5	CP	2.12	61.2	0.96	2.082	CP_low
3	CP	2.16	61.0	1.91	2.142	CP_high
7	-	2.00	66.1	-	2.080	plain

hybrids generally absorbed more energy compared to the plain laminates. However, the spread of the test data, from 2.05J to 4.54J, also increased with increasing impact energy. From these results, it was unclear of the real influence of the metal wires as the plain laminates absorbed an amount of energy that was within this spread.

The influence of the metal wires was more notable with the impact energy-damage area graph, Figure 3(b). The increase in absorbed energy with impact energy was accompanied by an increase in damage area. After impact at 7J, the resulting damage area was notably less with the hybrids than with the plain laminates. Therefore the impact energy was dissipated in a way that restricted the damage area. The discrepancy between the absorbed energy and damage area was due to the presence of the matrix-rich wire layer, which was able to locally plastically deform upon impact hence absorbing energy. A dent in the surface of the laminate resulted. As the impact energy was increased, the difference in damage area between the plain and the hybrid laminates reduced, but the plastically deformed dent on the surface was deeper and more evident. This means that at higher impact energies, the properties of the surface layer became less important than the bottom layer, i.e. beyond a certain impact energy level, the effect of the metal wire layer became minimal.

It was mentioned that there was a difference in the wire direction relative to the adjacent glass fibre direction for laminates UD_low and UD_high. As an example, the UD_high results were separated and highlighted by their original nomenclature of laminates 1 and 9 in both graphs in Figure 3. Laminate 1 did not perform consistently better than that of laminate 9, and vice versa, over the range of impact energies tested, highlighting that there was little difference with the wire arrangement. In addition, no particular laminate group performed differently to any of the others and therefore the influence of metal volume fraction was shown to have little influence when placed on the impact face.

Figure 4 shows the force-time plots for the plain and one of the hybrid laminates, in this case, that of the UD_high. At 7J, the plain laminates the force on the laminate reached a peak before reducing to zero as the impactor rebounded. The hybrid laminate reached a peak but maintained this force for a longer period of time before returning to zero. A peak plateau therefore resulted, which was due to the wire layer plastically deforming around the impactor. At 17J, the force plots were more similar in shape.

Figure 4(b) shows the force-displacement plots for the same plain and hybrid laminate. At 7J the curves were similar. At 17J, the hybrid laminate showed a more open curve indicating that more energy had been absorbed.

Figure 5 shows selected plates after impact at the lowest and highest impact energies. The white area indicates the extent of the damage caused by delaminations and matrix cracking. No fibre damage, i.e. breakage, occurred at any of the impact energies. On the top surface, matrix cracking due to the impactor resulted in permanent indentation for all laminates. At all impact energies, delaminations occurred between the layers of the lower half of the laminate. On the back side, delamination between the last two layers and cracking parallel the fibre direction occurred, forcing push-out of the glass layer, the extent of which was dependent on the impact energy. At the lowest impact energy little differences between the plates were observed. At the higher impact energy

(a) Absorbed energy

(b) Damage area

Figure 3 Impact energy graphs for plain and hybrid laminates with the metal placed on top. Each graph contains a trend line for the plain laminates.

(a) Force-time

(b) Force-displacement

Figure 4 Force graphs for representative laminates impacted with the metal wires placed on top.

differences in damage area were also similar in appearance, as the bottom glass layer offered relatively little resistance to damage propagation parallel to the fibres. The deformation of the surface was particularly evident on the CP_high laminate.

Figure 5 Visual inspection of specimens impacted with the metal wires placed on top.

Impact tests - metal wires on bottom face

Figure 6(a) shows the absorbed energy versus impact energy graph for the laminates impacted with the metal wires placed on the bottom (rough) face. The plain laminates were also tested with the rough face towards the impactor. As with the results of the previous section, there was also a spread of test data but the influence of the metal wire layer could more clearly be seen. At the lowest impact energy, the hybrids generally absorbed more energy than the plain laminates, but this behaviour was reversed as the impact energy increased. It should also be noted that the absorbed energy for the plain and hybrid laminates was greater than those presented in the previous section, and was attributed to the surface quality of the laminates. On the rough face, the impact force of the impactor was spread over a greater area while the smooth face was more epoxy-rich, creating a buffer, or cushion, effect. These two effects resulted in greater absorbed energy, and was also found with Ross *et al.*[2].

The influence of impact energy on damage area also showed a clear trend, Figure 6(b). At 7J, there was very little difference in damage area between all of the laminates. However, as the impact energy increased, the damage area became significantly lower than that of the plain laminates. Considering the absorbed energy and damage area, no particular hybrid laminate group could be shown to have superior impact properties compared to the rest. Generally, the difference in impact behaviour within each of the laminate groups was greater compared to the results of the previous section, particularly seen with CP_med. As the scatter between the plain laminates was small, this effect

may be attributed to where the hybrid laminate was impacted and wire/matrix adhesion, and will be discussed in further detail later.

As a check once again whether there was a difference in impact properties within each laminate group, the UD_low and UD_high results were separated and highlighted by their original nomenclature of laminates 4 and 8 and laminates 1 and 9, respectively, in both graphs in Figure 6. It was expected that as the greatest damage area occurred on the bottom side of the laminate, placement of the metal wires relative to the adjacent glass layer would be more important, especially with increasing impact energy. In other words, the metal wires would be more effectively placed perpendicularly to the adjacent glass fibres, as was the case with laminates 8 and 9, to prevent crack propagation and push-out of the glass layer. Again laminates 1 and 4 did not perform consistently better than that of laminates 9 and 8, and vice versa, over the range of impact energies tested, and therefore the wire direction had little influence. As with the metal wires placed on the top side, no particular laminate group performed differently to any of the others and therefore the influence of metal volume fraction was shown to have little influence.

The behaviour of the plain and hybrid laminates was further investigated with the force-time and force-displacement plots. Figure 7(a) shows an example of the force-time plot for the plain and hybrid laminates, in this case, that of the CP_med. At 7J the profiles were similar but at 17J were notably different. The plot for the plain laminate increased with time to the peak force, which was lower than that of the hybrid laminate. The lower peak force resulted from the bottom glass layer splitting and was pushed-out through the back of the laminate due to the impactor. A more gradual decrease in slope after the peak force was observed with the hybrid laminate. While the bottom glass layer in the case of the hybrids was also split and some individual wires pushed-out, the damage occurred over a longer period of time. Poorer adhesion of the wire to the epoxy matrix compared with the glass fibres, debonding occurred allowing the wires to slide through the matrix, which may have contributed to preventing sudden damage, and absorb more energy.

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(b) Damage area

Figure 6 Impact energy graphs for plain and hybrid laminates with the wires placed on the bottom. Each graph contains a trend line for the plain laminates.

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Figure 7(b) shows the accompanying force-displacement plot for the plain and CP_med laminates. At 7J, the curve of the hybrid laminate was more open than that of the plain, indicating that more energy had been absorbed. This may have been due to the greater

straining capability of the metal wire layer for the deformation at this low energy. Hence increased absorbed energy was observed because the entire laminate was able to deform more than with the plain laminate, without increasing the damage area. At 17J, the peak force was reached at the same displacement for both the laminates, but more severe damage occurred with the plain laminate as the peak was approached, indicated by the lower gradient initiated at around 4.5mm displacement. After peak load was reached, the plain laminate deflected further, indicating sudden damage, as was seen in the force-time plot and this was not seen with the hybrid. In this case, the wire layer served to restrict the absorbed energy. Crack propagation and delamination was reduced due to the reinforcing effect of the wires, and will be described more fully in the discussion. Hence the residual stiffness of the laminate was greater and more energy was returned to the impactor.

Figure 7 Force graphs for representative laminates impacted with the metal wires placed on the bottom.

Figure 8 shows selected plates after impact at the lowest and highest impact energies. At the lower energy, it was already clear that the presence of the wire layer restricted the damage propagation along the fibre direction in the bottom glass layer. At the higher energy, the restriction of damage area was even more pronounced as delamination and damage to the bottom glass layer was reduced.

DISCUSSION

It has been shown that at the lowest impact energy investigated, placement of the metal wires on the top of the laminate, impact side, resulted in a smaller damage area for the same absorbed energy compared to the plain laminates. However, the effect of the metal wires reduced with increasing impact energy. Conversely, placement of the metal wires on the bottom of the laminate resulted in increased contribution, particularly in terms of damage area, of the metal wires with increasing impact energy. The reason for the differences in impact behaviour with wire placement was attributed to the contribution of the bottom layers compared to the top. It is already known [3] that thin laminates experience the greatest damage at the bottom plies, on the opposite side to the impacted side, due to the flexibility of the system.

Figure 8 Visual inspection of specimens impacted with the metal wires placed on the bottom.

Figure 9(a) shows the bottom-side of an impacted hybrid laminate, with the delamination between the 3rd and 4th layer highlighted. The metal wire layer beneath showed no evidence of damage, and hence was not affected by the delamination.

It was expected that the hybrid laminates would allow for greater energy absorption due to the ductility of the metal wires. In particular, this effect was expected to be more pronounced with wires placed on the bottom of the laminates. However, the opposite trend was found as the laminate absorbed less energy compared to the plain laminates. Two reasons were attributed to the lower absorbed energy observed: the first due to stiffness and the second due to restriction of damage propagation. The presence of the metal wires increased bending stiffness, as well as the thickness, of the hybrid laminates, increasing impact resistance. Observation of the hybrids with the wires placed on the bottom of the laminate showed that the wires were pulled out due to splitting of the adjacent glass layer, Figure 9(b). A small amount of energy was likely absorbed through the pull-out process and local plastic straining, and the effect was that crack propagation was restricted in the glass layer. In addition, the wires served to reinforce the bottom layer against the high flexural (tensile) stresses experienced during impact. As the splitting of the glass layer was reduced, the stiffness was great enough to prevent further deflection of the laminate. In this way, delamination propagation was also reduced and hence the hybrid laminate was able to return more energy to the impactor, reducing the absorbed energy compared to the plain laminates.

The differences in impact behaviour became more distinct with increasing impact energy for the hybrids with the wires placed on the bottom-side, as the metal wires were allowed to strain slightly and hence contribute more fully during the impact event. It has

Figure 9 Images of hybrid laminates impacted at 7J (left) and 17J (right) and with the metal wires on the bottom-side.

been shown that even with such low volume fractions investigated, the effect of metal wire additions is substantial when placed at the bottom face of the laminate, although little difference was found between the different hybrids investigated. The reason for the apparently random data scatter may have been due to where the impactor hit the laminate in relation to the position of the wires. If the wire was directly underneath the impactor nose, it was able to fully contribute to the strain of the bottom layer. Slight misalignment would have reduced this effect. In addition as the wire/matrix adhesion was poor, the extent of wire pull-out was not controllable, which also contributed to the scatter. Considering the hybrids as a whole, at the highest impact energy investigated, an average drop of 9% and 20% in absorbed energy and damage area respectively was observed for a metal volume fraction of between 0.5-2%.

CONCLUSION

Stainless steel wires were added to the impacted (top) and non-impacted (bottom) side of glass/epoxy laminates and subjected to low velocity impact. Impact performance was measured in terms of absorbed energy, damage area and residual compression strength. Based on the experiments results, the following conclusions were made:

- Better impact resistance was found when the wires were placed on the bottom side of the laminate rather than the top compared to the plain laminates. The wires reinforced the bottom ply against the flexural tensile stress experienced during impact and increased the bending stiffness of the overall laminate.
- Contrary to expectation, absorbed energy decreased when the wires were placed on the bottom side of the laminate compared to the plain laminates. The wires themselves absorbed very little energy through pullout, but instead reinforced the laminate making it stronger and stiffer, resulting in reduced absorbed energy and damage area.
- There was very little difference in impact performance between the hybrid laminates with varying wire volume fractions, as hybrids with 0.5% volume fraction performed similarly to those with 2%. Considering the laminates with the wires on the bottom side, at the highest impact energy investigated, the average drop in absorbed energy and damage area of around 9% and 20% was

found. Such a performance increase was paired with an increase in density of less than 0.04g/cm^3

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